

Mobile Network Field Testing at HMP-2000

Bruce L. Gilbaugh*, Brian Glass†, Richard Alena‡
NASA-Ames Research Center
Moffett Field, CA 94035
650-604-4281
bgilbaugh@mail.arc.nasa.gov

Abstract—Future human planetary exploration field teams will need daily communications with their base and with mission control. A remote field wireless digital network will be a requirement for safe and productive human exploration. Proper selection of radio-frequency hardware and antennas will be vital to its success in remote, hostile environments. This paper reviews the communications techniques explored in the Mobile Exploration 2000 field season at the Haughton-Mars Project, which was located at a remote impact crater field science site in the Canadian Arctic. Results from 2.4GHz spread-spectrum signal-strength and data throughput tests, conducted during remote field deployments, show a marked variability with given hardware and antenna choices, with directional antenna performance less than expected from theory. Changing the antenna schemes for repeater-to-base and repeater-to-rover increased the rover's effective communication range to base camp to over 3km.

along with emergency communications scenarios to Mission Control. Scientists must provide an environment that closely resembles the surface of the planet to be visited as well as knowledge of the effects of local gravity, etc. Lastly, a place where the only things you have are what you bring with you. Having done just that this field season at the Haughton-Mars Project in the Wilderness of Nunavut, Canada, this paper will review the communications infrastructure and techniques explored. Six years ago work based at NASA's Ames Research Center proved that a wireless network was functionally practical in space by placing three laptop computer systems, a wireless access point, and two client PCMCIA transceiver cards aboard the Mir space station and successfully exchanging data between the three onboard computer systems using the wireless interfaces. Based upon the high degree of success of the Mir experiment, the implementation of a wireless network for keeping astronauts on manned planetary explorations in touch with their home base and ultimately with Mission Control using the proven wireless technology base was born. The Mobile Exploration Project (MEX) at Ames Research Center is designed to evaluate wireless technologies and explore their potential integration through simulations for the requirements of data, voice over IP, videoconference collaboration, and scientific data software applications. Ames' mobile architecture testbed is designed to integrate different components into a unified system and is currently under construction. For the past two years the MEX Project has been evaluating the use of FHSS (Frequency Hopping Spread-Spectrum) and DSSS (Direct Sequence Spread-Spectrum) network products to extend the wired capability of the Base Camp network computing LAN into the field. [1,2]

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION
2. EQUIPMENT BACKGROUND
3. SPREAD SPECTRUM TECHNOLOGY
4. ANTENNA BASICS
5. THE REPEATER-TO-BASE CAMP ANTENNA
6. THE REPEATER-TO-ROVER ANTENNA
7. THE ROVER ANTENNAS
8. CONCLUSION

1. INTRODUCTION

While NASA has achieved the goal of reaching the Moon, more distant planet exploration will require not only new technologies but new ways of thinking and communicating. Three basic elements are required for rehearsal of manned explorations to other planets. Members of a future manned planetary exploration group need to practice daily activity planning and reporting sessions for routine transmission

2. EQUIPMENT BACKGROUND

Typically this technology has been typically limited to a maximum range of 1000 feet in an outdoor setting with an unobstructed Line of Site (LOS). The basic specification for the radio transmitters providing this range was 1/10 Watt RF output into a dipole antenna. The maximum range attained for field seasons 1998 and 1999 was limited to just one quarter of a mile or 1,320 feet. This included the use of a repeater for extended range as well which should have provided a range of at least 1,600 feet or just over one third of a mile. Analysis of the equipment used to create the wireless network lead to one primary area that was determined to be incorrectly specified for such an application. High gain omni-directional antennas were

* Communications Engineer
† Senior Staff Scientist
‡ Computer Engineer

Standard IEEE copyright "0-7803-6599-2/01/\$10.00 © 2001 IEEE", U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. copyright.

deployed at the Base Camp, repeater, and roving terminal in an attempt to increase the effective operating range of the units. While the use of omni-directional antennas would eliminate any requirement for optimal pointing and positioning of antennas, the pattern of emission from the high gain antennas was not correctly understood. The requirement for the Houghton-Mars project and MEX in general is to evaluate the greatest possible distance attainable while maintaining reliable network connectivity and data throughput.

3. SPREAD SPECTRUM TECHNOLOGY

Spread Spectrum utilizes greater bandwidth and Signal-to-Noise ratios to create the same effective power but provide greater fidelity. As with any power equation, total power is the combination of two elements, in this case bandwidth and signal power. Two signals can have the same total equivalent power with either a large signal concentrated in a small bandwidth or a small signal spread over a large bandwidth. From a system standpoint throughput performance is increased and is referred to as "Process Gain" meaning that the fidelity of the received signal is greatly improved by sacrificing bandwidth. The advantage can be calculated using Claude Shannon's equation: [Equation 1]

$$C = W \log_2 (1 + S/N)$$

Where, C= Channel capacity in bits,
 Where: W = Bandwidth in Hertz,
 S = Signal Power, and
 N = Noise Power

Equation 1 - Shannon's Equation

Thus the Spread Spectrum signal is "hidden" in the electromagnetic noise floor and only receivers that know where to look can actually "lock on" to the signals located within. Within the frequency range that brackets a particular Spread Spectrum scheme lays the method of breaking up the information for transmission. Direct Sequence and Frequency Hopping techniques are the most commonly used with Frequency Hopping far outnumbering Direct Sequence. Figure 1 shows the typical DSSS (Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum) basic scheme.

Figure 1 - DSSS Frequency Scheme

In this scheme the 2.4 to 2.483 GHz is the Spectrum Range and there are three channels equally distributed within the spectrum range. A prescribed sequencing of "hops" from channel-to-channel is used to synchronize transmissions

between the receiver and the transmitter thus detecting the packets of information. Typical throughput for the DSSS scheme is in the neighborhood of 10 Mbps, far exceeding the throughput for a FHSS scheme at 1.6 Mbps.[7] In the FHSS scheme depicted in Figure 2, as many as 15 channels may be employed within the same Spectrum Range that contains only 3 channels in the DSSS system.

Figure 2 - FHSS Frequency Scheme

As in the DSSS scheme, the Frequency or Spectrum Range is 2.4 to 2.483 GHz however several noticeable differences readily emerge. This methodology has the transmissions actually hopping from one frequency to another. It is surely more difficult to control the 15 channels and the throughput is reduced. Generally in the past, the FHSS has been more widely used especially to provide network security that will be shown later.

The main reason FHSS is dominant in the PCS industry is the ability to "Cut Through" the interference or noise found in the RF spectrum. The FCC Part 15, Title 47, Section 15.247 in the Code of Federal Regulations (CFR) that governs these devices clearly states that they must accept any interference from outside sources without causing interference themselves. To simplify lets examine a system that uses two frequencies in both DSSS and FHSS modulation techniques. The DSSS format is typically lower in spectral density and uses prescribed or sequenced portions of the spectral range. Figure 3 shows the makeup of the DSSS two channel system created using two non-overlapping channels.

Figure 3 - DSSS Frequency Makeup

On the other hand the FHSS System hops around the spectrum range (indicated by the vertical displacement) thus

creating a higher spectral density but for shorter periods of time as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – FHSS Frequency Makeup

The following comparison gives a better view of the relative bandwidth consumed by both of the DSSS and FHSS technique channels. Looking at the same two channel systems in terms of Frequency Makeup, interference has less of an effect on the FHSS scheme. Remember they must accept the interference created by common appliances and other RF devices. Figure 5 shows the two systems being impacted by an interference signal. This interference signal is impacting two of the DSSS channels simultaneously while the FHSS channels "hop" around the interference signal.

Figure 5 –Interference vs. Channel Space

It is easy to see how the FHSS system is able to outperform the DSSS system. First the FHSS system is able to hop around the interference whereas the DSSS is unable to change its characteristics. This will result in the total loss of connectivity for the DSSS receiver because neither channel can pass any traffic. The FHSS traffic will surely be slowed but will not be disconnected. Thus the FHSS methodology has an inherent immunity to jamming and interference that is not typically found in the DSSS method.

Since the majority of the wireless products are primarily meant to be used by those with mobile computing power, i.e. laptop computers, there is also a concern about the effect of the unit drawing power from the laptop's battery thus limiting the total "On-Air Time". The devices are transmitters as well as receivers and when they transmit a significant draw is made compared to the receiver side of the

equation. Generally speaking, DSSS transmitters require very linear power amplifiers to maintain signal integrity and consistency. Unfortunately linear power amplifiers draw significantly more power when compared to the nonlinear power amplifiers that can be utilized by the FHSS designs. The result is less power draw on the laptop's battery and in turn a longer period of time available to the laptop device. Typical transmitter output power of devices in this category is a mere 100 mW or about 150 mA resulting in a cost to battery life of only 5% in most cases.

Although the remainder of this paper deals primarily with the use of antennas with FHSS technology, the concepts can be applied to both technologies of RF (Radio Frequency) Emission based hardware equally.

4. ANTENNA BASICS

The standard vertically polarized dipole antenna has a radiation pattern that resembles the shape of a donut indicated by the solid lines forming the radiation lobes in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – EMF transfer

When two antennas are tuned to interact at the same frequency, electromagnetic energy leaves the transmitting antenna and proceeds in the direction of the receiving antenna. The energy leaving the antenna grows both horizontally and vertically creating an area of interaction that excites the receiving antenna that is also tuned at a the same resonant frequency, thus allowing the transfer of the intended information present in the RF signal to the receiving station. When the radiation pattern of the vertically polarized antenna is viewed as presented in Figure 7 from a 45-degree angle, the pattern looks like the inner tube of a tire radiating or expanding in all directions equally from the antenna.

Fig. 7 – EMF Radiation Field

In order to increase the gain of an omni-directional antenna, the radiation pattern of the antenna is altered or modified to provide the required additional range. From the top view the only change is in the horizontal size of the pattern. Compare Figure 7, the emission pattern of a dipole antenna to that in Figure 8, the emission of an omni-directional antenna with 12 dB of gain.

Figure 8 – Altered Horizontal EMF Pattern

Remember that for every 3 dB of gain provided by the antenna design, the Effective Radiated Power (ERP) is doubled. Thus the emission of a 1/10th Watt RF signal into such an antenna effectively increases the ERP to .1 x 2 x 2 x 2 or 1.6 watts. As with any physics problem, "you don't get something for nothing". What changes in emission pattern are made to gain such an advantage then? Figure 8 shows how the pattern differs in the horizontal plane for the 12 dB omni-directional antenna. Notice that the radiation pattern has changed dramatically in the vertical direction. The top and bottom of the lobes have been squeezed together so that the new radiation pattern has a larger overall diameter in the horizontal plane but provides a very limited vertical radiation angle. The ability to transfer energy is increased between antennas by this redesign so long as they reside in similar vertical planes in relation to each other. If at least one element is located in another vertical plane or is vertically agile, this newly created pattern is less than satisfactory for the intended purpose. Since the radiation patterns are cut off at top and bottom any significant change in elevation will limit if not completely prohibit direct RF connectivity between units as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 – Vertical Elevation Incompatibility

5. REPEATER-TO-BASE CAMP ANTENNAS

The approach taken at this point was a re-examination of the requirements in terms of location, the number of fixed, and the number of mobile elements along the viability to utilize both the vertical and horizontal planes in conjunction with the total number of RF hop elements involved in the network infrastructure design. This year the HMP Base

Camp was located below an area referred to as Haynes Ridge. The distance between Base Camp and an optimal site for the repeater was a 1/2 mile LOS hop. The first challenge to be faced would be to provide a solid single hop link between the Base Camp antenna array and the input of the repeater module on Comm. Hill. Due to the elevation difference between Base Camp and Comm. Hill, using omni-directional antennas would neither be as effective as directional antennas nor allow the experimentation of the effect horizontal polarization. To accomplish this link an 18 dB parabolic antenna was chosen for use on the repeater input and mounted on a lightweight tripod shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 - repeater parabolic antenna

A 6 dB corner reflector antenna was installed for the Base Camp Access Point along with additional voice communications antennas also attached to a lightweight tripod. These antennas could be aimed toward each other in both vertical and horizontal planes in order to provide an optimal signal path since the two locations are stationary with respect to one another.

The use of parabolic and corner reflector antennas provided a means of positioning the RF emission pattern from each of the locations directing the energy to a specific non-moving

Fig. 11 - Base Camp Corner Reflector

target and provided increased gain for an increased ERP on both transmit and receive directions.

At one point in time an experiment was performed replacing the 6 dB corner reflector antenna on the Base Camp access point with the standard "rubber duck" dipole style antenna. With the use of this 1/2 wavelength (.5 λ) antenna at the base camp site providing no ERP gain, the access point site

was able to connect to the 18 dB parabolic antenna at the repeater site 1/2 mile away and maintain a link quality of 5. Software onboard the repeater device provided link strength quality on a scale of one to five with one being poor and five being the best possible. Two additional indicators are available for Received Signal Strength Indicator (or RSSI) and Packets per Second (or PPS). With the repeater installation complete on the Haynes Ridge site power was applied to the unit and link strength to Base Camp measured. The result was a solid link quality of five and available downloadable through-put of the wireless link to a server located at Base Camp was measured at 30 packets per second or 2.1 Kbps with an RSSI value of 159 while downloading a large digital picture file using the Netscape browser application. The successful test of this connection proved that a high quality link of more than 1/2 mile is possible on a single hop. Indeed this link could easily reach up to 3 miles and maintain a link quality between 3 and 4 as rated by the internal testing package.

6. THE REPEATER-TO-ROVER ANTENNA

Connectivity requirements within the mobile environment requires a provision for changing location in the vertical and horizontal planes and acknowledges that these changes may occur simultaneously. In this case, the first candidate for repeater output is most likely the omni directional antenna. The first consideration is that the emissions from the omni-directional antenna can overshadow or "swamp" the front end of the input receiver unit thus reducing or canceling the input link connection unless the antennas are at least 60 feet apart. A second design concern is that if it provides any significant gain, defined for this paper as being 9 dB or more, the emission pattern renders it unsuitable for large amounts of vertical change. Because these problems are found in the cellular telephone CDPD arena that also uses Spread-Spectrum emissions, antenna designers have created the sectoral antenna. (See Figure 12) The emission pattern of the sectoral antenna allows for selection of horizontal coverage up to 110 degrees between -3 dB points and up to 180 degrees between -6 dB points. Back scatter, the amount of signal presented behind to the rear of the antenna is held to a minimum to reduce or prevent adjacent antenna interference. So two out of three areas of concern are addressed by this antenna design. With only 10 degrees of vertical radiation pattern between the -3 dB points and a large physical presence, this antenna can be discounted as acceptable for the mobile mounted antenna. Provided it is mounted high enough and with a clear LOS in relation to its surrounding terrain, positioning the antenna at an angle so as to provide coverage to the highest opposite point, this antenna can provide a suitable vertical coverage pattern for the fixed portion of the mobile link. While the -3 dB points are at plus and minus 10 degrees, the -6 dB points extend to plus and minus 20 degrees. Combined with the mounting

Figure 12- Sectoral Antenna

angle this antenna provides a constant gain of up to 15 dB over the major portion (between all -3 dB point limits) of its radiation pattern.

7. THE ROVER ANTENNAS

Finally comes the selection of the antenna to be mounted on the All-Terrain Vehicle (ATV) or Rover that will communicate with the sectoral antenna on the repeater as it roams the test area. Since the repeater antenna is directional in nature the use of fixed directional antenna on the roving element is not practical. Unless a unit for self-pointing of the directional antenna is used, an omni-directional antenna is the first choice. This will provide 360-degree access to the repeater antenna regardless of the rover's direction of travel in relation to the antenna. As mentioned earlier, the gain of the antenna and the radiation pattern are inversely related in terms of vertical emission. Since the rover will be moving over a large range of vertical height an antenna must be identified that provides a maximum amount of gain while keeping a radiation pattern rich with vertical elements. A number of 5 dB omni-directional antennas are available for use that provide good vertical coverage with the caveat that the roving device will never be higher than the repeater. Barely visible is the one mounted next to a corner reflector atop the ATV antenna pod. The corner reflector was used to validate omni-directional selection. As a result the radiation pattern is modified to reduce the lower emission pattern in favor of the horizontal and upward vertical capability. Since the sectoral antenna is radiating "out and down" and the omni is radiating "out and up", there should be a good signal path for the roving element to connect to the repeater. Combining the gain values of both antennas a total of 20 dB of gain is available providing an ERP of 20 Watts with a 1/10th Watt actual power output. The rover is then tested incrementally to determine the longest viable link length for this antenna combination and configuration. Test results taken at various distances and heights by the rover showed link qualities as high as 4 at up to 1.5 miles from the repeater site and link qualities of 2 and 3 at distances up to 2.5 miles. During one traverse to Trinity Lake, a distance of 1.5 miles from Com Hill, the pen based computer tablet was removed from the ATV and carried a distance of approximately 120 yards away from the ATV which contained yet another repeater onboard for just this purpose. At a distance of 2 miles plus 120 yards from Base Camp, solid wireless Internet connections were established to several well-known web sites such as Yahoo.com, etc. From the HMP Base Camp the wireless signal was transferred via a small, wired LAN to a DSSS wireless link up to the satellite ground station on a hill overlooking Base Camp. That ground station transmitted the signals via geo-synchronous orbiting satellite back to a ground station in a lower elevation of Canada at the CRC where it was interfaced with the Internet. Additionally a

Figure 13 ATV Pod

camera onboard the rover was sending live color video images through a streaming JPEG server, also onboard the rover, back to Mission Control at Johnson Space Flight Center in Houston, Texas, via the combination of wired and wireless computer LANs and satellite networks. Test data shown in the following three chart sequences were

assembled from the data gathered during link testing sessions. Rover location was obtained from onboard GPS readings. The Link Strength and RSSI data shown is calculated by internal software within the Proxim devices. Throughput was a measurement provided during downloads or jpeg video streaming input via Netscape 4.7 data bar.

Wireless Network Link Data for HMP/MEX 2000

Base Camp Baseline Data

Lat	Long	Altitude (feet)	Repeater Distance (mi)	Test Link	Link Strength	RSSI	Throughput (Kbytes/sec)
75 25.985	89 51.792		0		0		
75 25.771	89 50.241		0.51	BB	5	198	36.8

Traverse Data Taken 7/20/00

ID	Lat	Long	Altitude (feet)	Repeater Distance (mi)	Test Link	Link Strength	RSSI	Throughput (Kbytes/sec)
COM	75 25.77	89 50.17	735	0.1	BSA	5	195	19.5
14	75 26.86	89 52.04	681	1.37	BSA	3	135	12
17	75 27.15	89 51.41	803	1.63	BSA	2	127	3
18	75 26.98	89 53.06	734	1.63	BSA	4	142	19.5
19	75 27.01	89 54.02	763	1.81	BSA	1	125	2
20	75 27.11	89 56.12	786	2.31	BSA	0	0	0
21	75 26.88	89 54.84	862	1.87	BSA	2	125	0.5
22	75 26.98	89 52.76	786	1.58	BSA	2	128	3.5
	75 26.55	89 51.62		1	BSA	3	137	2.5

Traverse Data Taken 7/22/00

ID	Lat	Long	Altitude (feet)	Repeater Distance (mi)	Test Link	Link Strength	RSSI	Throughput (Kbytes/sec)
31	75 25.28	89 48.87	524	0.67	BSA	0	0	0
32	75 25.17	89 48.65	501	0.81	BSA	2	136	0.5
33	75 24.88	89 49.27	488	1.06	BSA	2	124	1.5
34	75 25.11	89 47.87	511	1.00	BSA	3	128	3
35	75 25.27	89 48.06	475	0.83	BSA	2	127	3
36	75 25.42	89 48.18	504	0.69	BSA	2	125	3
37	75 25.57	89 48.21	553	0.60	BSA	2	124	4
None	75 25.70	89 48.42	580	0.50	BSA	3	127	1.5
38	75 25.82	89 48.43	632	0.50	BSA	0	0	0

8. CONCLUSION

The wireless network environment viable for manned planetary exploration use provided the correct antenna selections are available for deployment. The MEX project field season 2000 has validated not only the process for the selection of antennas for the simulation test bed being built at Ames but how critical proper selection of antennas really is. Changing the antenna scheme increased the rover's communication distance to Base Camp from 1/4 of a mile to over 3 miles.

The data rate to combine voice, data, and real-time video serving on the backbone of the wireless LAN will have to be greater than 2.0 Mbps to allow for synchronization overhead and still provide enough bandwidth for the combined information sources and to deal with multipath and environmental condition interference. During the testing of the MEX system, problems were experienced with the interaction of the DSSS wireless link to the ground station. It was determined that the FHSS system could easily interfere with the DSSS system primarily because of the DSSS system's highly sensitive receiver. One experiment that was cut short by inclement weather was to run the FHSS system Repeater-to-Base Camp link on a horizontal polarization while the DSSS system was required to operate in a vertically polarized mode due to the available antennas. Continued testing at Ames' Testbed for Intelligent Mobile Technologies (IMT) and Mobile Exploration Projects (MEX) will provide the opportunity for future testing of system components, integration concepts, and interference problems more completely prior to remote field test scenarios.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank the NASA-Ames Haughton-Mars Project for permitting us to participate in their field season activities; for the support provided by Dr. Pascal Lee and Dr. Kelly Snook who lead the expedition for HMP 2000, and we would like to thank Dr. Stephen Braham of Simon Fraser University of Vancouver, BC, Canada for his consultations and direct support of the satellite and base camp links used for MEX testing.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alena, Richard. E. Yaprak, S. Lamouri. Modeling A Wireless Network For International Space Station, 1999. IEEE Aerospace Conference.
- [2] Alena, Richard. Wireless Network Experiment – Risk Mitigation Experiment 1306. 1996. report on STS-74/76-Mir20 experiment for the Phase One International Space Station Program.
- [3] Dreher, Richard. The Comprehensive Guide to Wireless Technologies. 1999. APDG Publishing Fuquay-Varina, NC
- [4] Held, Gilbert. Internetworking LANs and WANs. 1998. John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- [5] Horak, Ray. Communications Systems & Networks. 1999. M&T Books. Foster City, CA
- [6] Kuo, Effelsberg, Aceves, et. al. Multimedia Communications Protocols and Applications. 1998. Prentice-Hall
- [7] Proxim Corporation. RangeLAN2 Technical Reference Guide. 2000. Proxim, Inc. USA
- [8] Roberts, Randy. Virginia Polytechnic Institute's Spread Spectrum Introduction. 1999. Spread Spectrum Scene - Online magazine @ www.sss.org
- [9] Configuring and Using Extension Points in wireless LANs. Proxim White Paper. 1998. Online @ <http://www.proxim.com>
- [10] Comparing FH and DS Wireless LAN Technologies. Proxim Presentation. 1998. Online @ <http://www.proxim.com>
- [11] Digital Communications: Spread Spectrum – It's not just for breakfast anymore! Steve Bible, N7HPR. 1999. Online @ <http://www.tapr.org/ss>

Bruce Gilbaugh is a member of the Intelligent Mobile Technology (IMT) Lab and the Mobile Exploration (MEX) hardware design and implementation group at NASA-Ames Research Center. He designed the mechanical hardware mounting and ATV implementation schemes for MEX 2000 testing during the HMP. Bruce holds an AS degree in RF Communications Systems and Computer Networks, a BS in Information System Management from the University of San Francisco and is currently working on an MS in Telecommunications Management at Golden Gate University.

Dr. Brian J. Glass has been on the staff of NASA-Ames Research Center since 1987. He has led projects in automated reasoning (for Space Station and SETI health management), surface air traffic control (the Surface Movement Advisor, for which he shares a patent), and research groups in intelligent, adaptive control systems. In addition to his education and interests in engineering and computer science, he acquired an additional graduate degree in geophysics in 1992 focused on morphological models of scarp-like landforms. Brian is currently responsible for information and automation technologies in the Human Exploration Office and works closely with the Center for Mars Exploration. Over the past two summers, Brian has conducted field experiments at terrestrial analog sites in the Arctic to test human-centered computing concepts for future Mars geological exploration.

Richard Alena is a Computer Engineer and the Group Lead for the Intelligent Mobile Technology (IMT) Lab and the Mobile Exploration System (MEX) testbed being created at NASA Ames Research Center. The IMT team integrates mobile hardware and software components into unique systems capable of extending human performance aboard spacecraft during flight and payload operations. He has a MSEE&CS from University of California, Berkeley.

